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Guidelines for training in participating RIs

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
ADDIE	Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation and Evaluation
LL	Living Lab
LOs	Learning Objectives
M&E	Monitoring and Evaluation
M4C	MICROBES-4-CLIMATE
RI	Research Infrastructure
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, Time-bound
SUEP	Stakeholder and user engagement plan
TNA	Transnational Access. Allowing third party researchers from a foreign institution to access an organisation's research facilities and services.
VA	Virtual Access. Allowing third-party researchers to access an organisation's cloud, data centre, and/or its other IT facilities and services.
WP(s)	Work Package(s). A set of related activities within a project.

Concept	Definition
Access manager	Manager of access and service provision in a Research Infrastructure
Installation	Facility or service for the implementation of a specific service, a synonym a facility specifically with respect to access to experimental services

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About the project

Terrestrial biodiversity and ecosystems are being challenged by climate change and environmental degradation. Moreover, threats to agricultural and forestry systems represent some of the most serious environmental and socio-economic menaces that the planet and humanity are facing. Climate change is recognised as a major hindrance to the regulation of global natural cycles, which affects biodiversity, and enhances ecosystem loss. Microorganisms, despite being overlooked and not usually considered in the context of climate change, are key for the healthy maintenance of the biosphere. The many impacts of climate change on the assembly, functions and occurrence of microbiomes are still not fully understood. The intricate interactions and relations between microbes-plants-soil, their impacts on crop (plant) productivity, health and efficiency, as well as how they are impacted by climate change is still largely unknown. The inner workings of ecosystems still need to be mapped, as well as the microbiome influence on climate change mitigation and adaptation. MICROBES-4-CLIMATE is intended for the global community of researchers to provide easy access to a selected cluster of Research Infrastructures and their integrated services coupled with training and scientific and/or technical support. The MICROBES-4-CLIMATE project stands out as a Transnational Access programme, which will offer the possibility to users to conduct research leveraging microbes and ecosystems' interactions, its roles in climate change resilience, mitigation and adaptation. This high quality access will drive new frontiers of knowledge and incentivise applied research for the harnessing of plant-microbiome interactions to improve the climate resiliency of plants/crops. This could ultimately bolster the resilience and sustainability of food systems.

Executive Summary

“D7.4. Guidelines for training in participating RIs” deliverable serves as a comprehensive framework for the coordination, design and implementation of comprehensive, efficient and effective training initiatives within the M4C project. To this extent, this deliverable provides a detailed and complete overview of the most relevant principles, issues, elements and challenges of training activities and programmes development and delivery. The main purpose is to equip staff of the participating RIs with critical standards and guidelines, facilitating the development of high quality training products and ensuring the success of the training activities throughout the project. These guidelines, established and consolidated project-wise, should also support the alignment and standardisation of all training initiatives regardless of who delivers them and where they are delivered.

The document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1 introduces the main focus of the document, as well as the rationale that led to its development.
- Chapter 2 describes the approach followed to develop the guidelines contained in the document and details the preliminary steps adopted to better clarify the current situation in M4C participating RIs.
- Chapter 3 presents an overview of some of the most relevant Training Principles and Methodologies for the project framework of (training) actions.
- Chapter 4 illustrates the most important steps of the Training Cycle, hence eliciting guidelines for training products and activities design, development and delivery.
- Chapter 5 briefly looks at potential training products that the project partners may develop and deliver, and presents an online training platform that could host these products.
- Chapter 6 concludes with a number of recommendations for future training actions.
- Chapter 7 lists the references used in developing the present document.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1. Introduction

The current deliverable is part of the Task 7.3 of the project. The task focuses mainly on the organization and development of the training programme.

The task also focuses on establishing a standard methodology and guidance for the development of training courses and workshops within every RI, where potential users will be invited to directly use the services under the support of RI staff. This is the specific focus of the Deliverable 7.4.

The rationale behind this work is the lack of clear and structured methodologies and guidelines for trainers when developing training programmes. This lack of structure can lead to less efficient training, extra time spent to develop such training and, finally, less well-trained users. We aimed to bring a unified standardized methodology that helps solving such issues, especially in the multi RI environment where multiple RIs can benefit from a consistent approach.

Task 7.3 started with a survey circulated among project partners to better understand both the partners' training capacities, experience and needs, as well as the users typologies, categories, characteristics and needs. This was deemed crucial for designing and generating a comprehensive and effective training methodology and guidance document. In fact, it allowed a more precise and accurate knowledge of the training initiatives' target users and their specific needs.

Thanks to the survey, Task 7.3 was also able to identify additional information about users' major and most critical knowledge gaps (e.g., training cycle concept and steps).

This deliverable, therefore, provides additional information about such concepts, ensuring that all the training organizers follow the most relevant training quality standards and methodologies.

The scope and main objective of Deliverable 7.4 is to provide all the RI infrastructures involved in the MICROBES-4-CLIMATE (M4C) project with a training design and development guide. This guide will ensure the delivery of high-quality training activities, courses and workshops during the project.

Chapter 2

M4C Training Approach

2. M4C Training Approach

The identification and consolidation of methodologies, standards and guidelines is a critical element in the design and development of training and learning programmes. This is particularly important when these guidelines aim to enhance the effectiveness of training initiatives across various organisations, RIs, and topics. Training development relies on several best practices, such as establishing clear training objectives, utilizing diverse training methods to accommodate various learning styles, and fostering collaborative learning environments.

A structured and comprehensive approach to establishing such methodologies, standards and guidelines – involving a series of steps that include needs assessment; learning objectives formulation; content design and development; training programmes delivery; and, evaluation – is crucial for the success of these training initiatives. This ensures relevance, engagement, alignment with the strategic objectives of involved RIs, and success in enhancing skills and knowledge of their respective target audiences.

As mentioned above, the first step consists in identifying specific skills and knowledge gaps within the participating RIs and their target audiences. This process usually includes collecting data through surveys, interviews, and observations to analyse current competency levels and define the required learning outcomes.

Following this approach, the Task 7.3 action started with a thorough assessment of the current situation among participating RIs, collecting and analysing data to identify skill gaps and learning requirements within the various organisations. To this extent, a survey was conducted to assess training needs, participation levels, and familiarity with training methodologies among research infrastructure professionals.

The following paragraphs present the key findings of the survey about the needs for training of facility/service managers, service users, and trainers in relation to the Transnational Access ([access the survey here](#)).

2.1 Results of the survey assessing training needs of facility/service managers, service users, and trainers in relation to the Transnational Access

2.1.1 Respondents and their training experience

1. “Does your Research Infrastructure/Institution provide your role with resources and support for training?”

- a. For those who answered “yes” in the previous question, here is the type of the training support they receive from the organization:

2. “Do you participate in any formal or informal working group about training?”

6 out of 22 respondents participate in training working groups.

3. “How familiar are you with the training cycle and principles?”

As it is possible to observe from the plot, a large portion of the facility managers are not familiar with the training cycle and principles. This indicates that more focus should be put on this topic to bring all the facility managers knowledge up to the desired level.

4. “How familiar are you with the concept, and the writing, of learning objective/s?”

This plot shows that respondents are generally more familiar with the learning objectives compared to the training cycle. However, overall familiarity is rather low, suggesting that this topic also deserves significant attention.

5. “How confident do you feel in designing impactful training sessions?”

Again, a higher level of respondent familiarity is observed when compared to the previous question. However, more than a half of the respondents indicated a very low confidence level (score < 5, 13 respondents). This highlights the need for target support/guidelines and methodologies to help the respondents design impactful training sessions.

6. “How confident do you feel in devising tests, exercises and assessments that can truly evaluate the learning progress?”

Here it is possible to observe an interesting distribution of responses. There is both a significant group of people who are very confident in learning process evaluation (score > 5, 9 respondents) and a group with a low confidence (score < 5, 13 respondents).

7. “How familiar are you with online training methodologies and tools?”

Here it is possible to observe a wide distribution of responses. However, the overall familiarity with online training methodologies could be higher - more than half of respondents indicated a low familiarity (score <5, 12 respondents).

8. “How familiar are you with face-to-face training methodologies?”

Here it is possible to observe that a larger fraction of the respondents is familiar with face-to-face training methodologies.

9. “How many training events did you deliver and/or participate to deliver?”

Here we could observe that the largest portion of respondents delivered/participated at between 0 and 5 trainings.

To summarize the findings on respondents and their training experience, the following key points can be highlighted:

- more focus should be put on training cycle and learning objectives concepts explanation and outline;
- clear guidelines and methodologies are needed to increase respondents’ confidence in the overall training design;
- online training methodologies might require more attention than face-to-face training methodologies, since the familiarity with the former ones is lower. This is important if a significant amount of online training sessions are planned, in particular by the respondents who indicated lower familiarity with them.

2.1.2 Target audience

10. “How well do you know your target audience?”

As it is possible to observe from the graph, most respondents know their audience either well or quite well.

11. “Tell us the main characteristics of your target audience.”

*broad refers to when a large number of various categories was mentioned. For example, researchers, private companies, federal government agencies, regulatory agencies, etc.

2.1.3 Training activities

12. “Do you plan to organize any training activities at your Research Infrastructure or its Installations during Transnational Access?”

Surprisingly, only 7 out of 22 respondents indicated “Yes” to this question. The T7.4 members hypothesis is that most respondents are interested in organizing training activities. However, these training activities might not occur during the TNA.

A few additional insights:

- Some respondents answered “No” probably because they are not sure about the exact timing of the training, even though they might occur during the TNA period.
- Some are open to provide training even if currently there is no training planned/scheduled for them.
- Some consider that it is not necessary to organize training since users will always be accompanied by the trained staff.

For the 7 respondents that indicated “Yes” on the abovementioned question, a follow up was done to better understand the planned training activities. Here are a few additional insights:

- the target audience for the planned training activities is mainly researchers;
- the topics of the planned training activities mainly include: imaging and image processing, data analysis and AI, fungal biodiversity and isolation, service basic knowledge;
- there seems to be a degree of flexibility in the training format (online/offline), however the final choice depends on the training itself;
- the anticipated length of the trainings is between 1 and 15 hours;
- only in 2 out of 7 cases the trainer has been already selected.

2.1.4 Training needs

The key responses are provided in Chapter 5 of the survey “Suggestions for a M4C Training Plan”.

13. “As a facility/service manager, what are the most common challenges or obstacles users face when engaging with the M4C services that you manage?”

(15 out of 22 respondents indicated challenges).

Note: it could have been advisable to formulate the question as follows: “As a facility/service manager, what are the most common challenges or obstacles users face when engaging with the M4C services/*other projects services* that you manage?”. This would allow respondents to share experiences based on their involvement with other projects as well.

14. “What skills or knowledge do you think users should possess before accessing the M4C services that you manage?”

(20 out of 22 respondents indicated challenges).

As shown in the plot, the main skills/knowledge identified as required are: subject in-depth knowledge and data analysis.

In terms of subject in-depth knowledge, the main areas highlighted include: microbiology, plant physiology, cryopreservation, and bacteriology.

15. “In your opinion, what types of training should facility/service managers provide to users at the installation level?”

(19 out of 22 respondents indicated challenges).

It is interesting to note that a significantly larger fraction of respondents indicated “Data Analysis” as the main challenge. However, only one respondent indicated that the respective training is needed. This mismatch would be interesting to follow-up to understand the underlying reasons. One possible explanation is the logistical difficulty of organizing data analysis courses at each location. In such cases, a centralized course could be organized and coordinated training sessions could be considered to solve this issue when a project is running. It is also important to note that one of the participating RI is planning a training activity on data analysis and AI.

16. “Do you have any additional insights, suggestions, or experiences to share regarding user training needs?”

Regarding this question, it appears important to report the following comment: *“Many times, training sessions are not entirely clear to users, perhaps because they are not tailored to their level of experience with the topic. In my opinion, it is crucial to understand the audience to adapt the content appropriately”.*

This is indeed a critical point to understand the audience when developing a training. This will be further highlighted in the next Chapter of this deliverable.

Chapter 3

Overview of relevant Training Principles and Methodologies

3. Overview of relevant Training Principles and Methodologies

Training is a dynamic process designed to assist individuals to learn, re-learn and reinforce existing knowledge, skills and abilities. Effective training is about transfer and retention of relevant information and development of skills and attitudes that can be transferred back to the workplace. Successful training enables individuals and organisations to do things better, faster, easier and with higher quality.

Learning and training principles encompass a range of theories and methodologies that guide the process of acquiring knowledge and skills in various educational and professional contexts. These principles, which have evolved significantly over time, are widely applicable across diverse fields, audiences and learning styles. They provide a foundation for designing learning and training experiences that foster active engagement, experiential learning, and meaningful interactions among learners. Understanding these principles is crucial for trainers that aim to create engaging, effective, and adaptable learning environments that meet the needs of learners.

On the other end, training methodologies encompass a range of approaches used to deliver instructional content and facilitate learning. These methodologies are selected based on various factors, including training objectives, audience's needs, and available resources.

Effective training programs often utilize a combination of principles and methodologies to cater to diverse learning styles and maximize engagement and retention. This Chapter provides an overview of the most relevant training principles and methodologies vis-à-vis the project goals and the future training initiatives objectives.

3.1 Adult learning and engagement

The learning process of an adult is different from the learning process of a child. To deliver successful training, it is paramount to clearly understand the special characteristics of adults when it comes to learning. Although individual differences exist, this paragraph presents the most important general principles of adult learning.

Adults are willing to learn those things that they believe will help them perform a task or solve a problem. To maximize engagement, training approaches should connect content to the real-life challenges that adult learners face, helping them to see the direct impact on their professional and personal development. Stimulating intrinsic motivation is crucial, as adults tend to learn best when they perceive the personal value of the material being presented.

Adults bring a wealth of knowledge and experience to learning environments and are often willing to share it. Effective training initiatives should build on this aspect and make use of adults' knowledge and

experience, thus privileging participatory methods and encourage learners to share their knowledge and experience.

Adults enjoy being active during the learning process and interacting with each other. They appreciate being engaged and having fun. Techniques such as peer teaching and interactive discussions can foster a collaborative learning environment, encouraging deeper understanding and critical thinking among participants.

Adults want to know why they should learn something before investing resources and time into a learning event. If the contextualization and the purpose of the training (overall goal, specific learning objectives, etc.) are missing, adults will not see the value of training initiatives. The consequence would most likely be low engagement, hindering training effectiveness.

Other factors contributing to disengagement include a lack of relevance and the perception that training is an unnecessary interruption to their work. Resistance to change is another common barrier among adult learners, who may be reluctant to adopt new methods or concepts due to established beliefs or routines. To mitigate this resistance, it is crucial to communicate the benefits of new training methods clearly and maybe even involve individuals in the development process.

3.2 Learning Styles

Human beings are created to learn, and learn new things continuously, sometimes even without being aware that they are learning. Humans constantly learn, both in more formal or informal settings. Moreover, adults learn differently. Besides having different preferences for learning, they may also favour different senses.

Learning styles refer to the various approaches and preferences individuals exhibit in the process of acquiring knowledge and skills. Understanding the various learning styles is integral to developing instructional strategies that enhance engagement and success in training. A trainer needs to take into account such differences in order to tailor teaching methods to suit diverse learner needs.

Over the years, various models have been proposed to categorize and understand the different learning styles individuals exhibit. The most widely recognized models include the VARK model and the Kolb Learning Style Inventory, among others.

The VARK model¹, categorizes learning preferences into four main styles: Visual, Auditory, Reading/Writing, and Kinesthetic. Each category represents a distinct way in which individuals prefer to engage with and process information. For example, visual learners benefit from diagrams and charts, auditory learners excel through discussions and lectures, reading/writing learners favor written text, and kinesthetic learners thrive on hands-on experiences.

¹ <https://vark-learn.com/introduction-to-vark/the-vark-modalities/>

On the other hand, the Kolb's model² identifies four learning styles based on the experiential learning theory: Concrete Experience, Reflective Observation, Abstract Conceptualization, and Active Experimentation. Effective learning involves a cycle that incorporates all four of these approaches, enabling learners to grasp and transform their experiences effectively. This model emphasizes the importance of engaging multiple learning processes to optimize understanding and retention.

Selecting appropriate and varied training methods is crucial for maximizing engagement and retention. Various approaches, such as workshops, e-learning, simulations, and blended learning, should be considered based on the training objectives, audience, and available resources. This step should also cater to different learning styles to enhance the overall effectiveness of the training. Training initiatives need to aim for offering various ways to learn, where:

- learning methods and ways of presenting information are varied;
- learners have different opportunities to show what they know and what they have learnt; and,
- learners are motivated and challenged in various ways.

3.3 Online vs. Face-to-Face Training

Online versus face-to-face training refers to the different methodologies used in professional training contexts, each offering unique advantages and challenges. Face-to-face training is characterized by direct interaction between instructors and learners in a physical setting, facilitating real-time feedback and interpersonal engagement. The rise of digital technology and the necessity for remote learning options, have led to the emergence and growing acceptance of online training formats, which became an essential component of training initiatives.

The effectiveness of training programs can vary significantly between online and face-to-face formats. Online training, notable for its flexibility, cost-effectiveness, and accessibility, allows participants to learn at their own pace and from various locations, breaking geographical barriers that often limit traditional classroom settings.

On the other hand, face-to-face training offers unique advantages that can enhance learning effectiveness. Direct interactions facilitate immediate feedback, allow instructors to address challenges and reinforce learning in real-time. Furthermore, the structured nature of in-person training helps maintain attendance and engagement, which can be challenging in an online format. Conversely, the reliance on in-person instruction can lead to challenges in scaling training programs across geographically dispersed teams.

In recent years, a third methodology gained popularity when blended and hybrid models were explored. These models seek to integrate the best elements of both approaches, fostering a dynamic learning

² <https://learningfromexperience.com>

environment that leverages the strengths of digital platforms while retaining the benefits of in-person engagement.

This said, the choice between online, face-to-face, and blended or hybrid training ultimately depends on the specific learning objectives, audience needs and content requirements of the training initiative under discussion. In addition, reflections on the best methodology to employ, must also consider diverse learning styles and organizational requirements to optimize engagement and retention.

Chapter 4

The Training Cycle

4. The Training Cycle

The Training Cycle is a systematic framework that outlines the process, and its essential steps, for creating and implementing effective training programs within organisations. Sometimes also referred to as instructional process, it is the process that ensures that a determined training action addresses the needs of its target audience, allowing it to achieve the expected results and create lasting and effective change. This process is crucial for ensuring that training is not only delivered but also impactful and aligned with both organizational goals and individual development needs.

This cycle encompasses five key steps or phases that should be explored in conceptualizing any training initiative or learning event: analysis, design, development, implementation and evaluation. These five steps constitute the instructional design model known as ADDIE.

Analysis is the first step of the training cycle and focuses on the identification of the needs of the beneficiaries and their organisation. Analysis is essential to determine whether training is the correct response to the needs of the target audience and, should that be the case, also helps to reflect on what type of training activity is the most appropriate for the specific case.

Design focuses on writing the learning objectives, defining the sequence and planning the time for the different sessions of the training. The design phase builds on the information collected during the analysis to create a training that meets the needs and the characteristics of the target audience.

Development goes hand in hand with design. Without a good design plan, developing a course can lead to many frustrating moments. Development focuses on the definition of the instructional strategy and the actual creation of the content and learning material that will be used during the training.

Implementation refers to the moment in which the training takes place. Implementation is about facilitating learning and ensuring that learners achieve the objectives defined during the design phase. Facilitation is the process through which learning is fostered. Trainers should not only ensure that knowledge and skills are transferred, but also that they are retained by learners, and eventually applied to their jobs, contributing to bring about a desired change at the organizational level.

Evaluation is a crosscutting process that helps to collect data and analyse if and how the training contributed to any change. Evaluation is an essential source of information and its importance cannot be overestimated. In general terms, evaluation refers to a systematic and objective assessment of an ongoing or completed project, programme or policy, its design, implementation and results. The aim of evaluation is to determine the relevance and fulfilment of objectives, efficiency, effectiveness, impact and sustainability.

The instructional design model is not a simple linear process that starts with analysis and moves on through stages to evaluation. Instead, each phase is interlinked, it is more like a connected circle, with the

end feeding back into the beginning, or even like a web with all of the aspects interconnected and leading to parts of each other. It is important to always keep this in mind and adapt the process as moving forward.

Needs assessment, program design, plan development, implementation, and evaluation. This framework is vital in enhancing workforce capabilities, improving performance, and ultimately driving organizational success. Each step will be discussed further in more detail in the next Chapters.

4.1 Analysis: defining training needs and target audience(s)

The first step of the training cycle is the analysis step, which focus on identifying the specific skills and knowledge gaps within the organisation. This phase is conducted through a needs assessment and an analysis of the available data. Combined together, assessment and analysis are key elements for designing a successful and effective training events, as they allow to determine whether training is the correct response to the needs of the audience, while also giving a clear indication of the training type to focus on.

The training needs assessment allows to compare a present level of competence of an audience with a desired level of competence, and to identify the actions that need to be put in place to fill the eventual gap between the two levels. It leads to identifying and analysing the specific training needs, in terms of knowledge and skills, required for the organisation and its employees to perform a specific activity. This step is crucial as it determines whether training is necessary and highlights the areas that require development. A comprehensive needs assessment serves as the foundation for the subsequent phases of the training cycle. In other words, the findings of assessment and analysis help to define the learning objectives of a training action.

Equally important to determining training needs is learning as much as possible about the target audience. Collecting information about the target audience is essential to have a clear picture in terms of personal characteristics (gender, age range), cognitive characteristics (educational level, language, prior knowledge of the subject, computer literacy), work characteristics (job roles, work responsibilities, work schedule), and social characteristics (interests and motivation). Assessing the target audience is a key step to identify not only the profile of the intended learners, but also to define a number of variables that will influence the entire training design process, such as the approach of the training and delivery methods that best suits learners' needs. The target audience analysis may be conducted as part of the needs assessment – many of the information on the target audience are derived from the data-gathering – or immediately after it.

The analysis phase involves collecting data through surveys, interviews, and observations to analyse the current performance levels and understand the missing required competencies. Various methods such as

surveys, performance appraisals, and feedback sessions can be employed to gather data on current skills, performance gaps, and future requirements.

Engaging partners, if any, in this stage is crucial to strengthen the relevance of the conclusions drawn and to enhance the applicability of the training solutions recommended.

4.2 SMART Learning Objectives and planning of sessions

After assessing and identifying the training needs of the target audience and collecting information on its characteristics, the next step is designing the training product.

The design phase builds on the information collected during analysis to create a training that meets the needs and the characteristics of the target audience. It goes hand in hand with the development phase: all the activities that will be carried out as part of the design phase will influence the development of the training, and vice-versa.

The design phase focuses on establishing and writing clear learning objectives, defining the sequence and content of the training program, and planning the time for the different sessions of the training. Finally, it also involves selecting the delivery format, which can range from classroom-based sessions to online training or blended learning approaches.

Establishing clear and measurable learning objectives is a paramount aspect of training design. These objectives serve as a roadmap for both trainers and trainees, guiding the instructional process and enabling effective evaluation of learning progress. First, these objectives need to be understandable and accessible to all stakeholders, ensuring that everyone involved is aligned on the training's purpose and goals. Second, these objectives serve not only as benchmarks for success, but also as a foundation for evaluating the effectiveness of the training program. By comparing the achieved outcomes with the intended goals, organisations can assess the training's success and identify areas for improvement.

Writing learning objectives can be translated as “beginning with the end in mind”. It involves determining what learners should expect to know or be able to do at the end of the training, and refer to the measurable performance that is desired by the end of the training.

Writing SMART learning objectives is a systematic approach to defining training goals that enhances effectiveness and outcomes of the learning process. The acronym SMART stands for Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound, encapsulating essential characteristics that contribute to the clarity and focus of learning objectives. This method promotes structured course design and fosters learners' engagement as it clearly articulates expectations and assessment criteria.

Specific refers to the clarity of the objective, detailing exactly what is expected from the learner. A specific objective eliminates ambiguity, providing a clear direction for both instruction and assessment. For

instance, instead of stating that students will "improve their writing skills," a more specific objective might be "students will compose and revise at least three essays, each receiving a score of 70% or higher"³. This clarity helps learners understand precisely what they need to accomplish.

Measurable involves defining how the success of the objective will be assessed. A measurable objective provides concrete criteria for evaluation, ensuring that both instructors and learners can track progress effectively. For example, setting a pass mark or specifying that students will demonstrate their understanding through projects or essays allows for quantifiable assessments of their learning.

Achievable ensures that the learning objectives set are realistic and attainable, considering the resources available and the learners' current capabilities. Objectives should be challenging yet within reach, motivating learners without overwhelming them⁴. This aspect is particularly important when training about specialized subjects, as it will be in the case of M4C TNA.

Relevant emphasizes the importance of aligning learning objectives with broader training and project goals and real-world applications. Objectives should resonate with learners, thereby increasing engagement and motivation.

Time-bound learning objectives include specific deadlines or timeframes for achieving the established objectives. Establishing a realistic timeline helps maintain focus and provides a sense of urgency, encouraging learners and enhancing the learning experience.

Bloom's Taxonomy, established in 1956, offers a hierarchical model for categorizing learning objectives, that trainers can use to ensure that their goals encompass a wide range of cognitive skills.⁵

Learning objectives are at the core of course design. They determine the structure of the training, the approach, the methodology, the time that will be spent on each session and how training will be evaluated. Implementing SMART learning objectives also allows trainers to create more structured and coherent course designs, guiding contents development and training delivery and facilitating the assessment process. Establishing a clear structure for training materials is vital for facilitating easy navigation and comprehension. The organization of content should follow a logical flow, potentially arranged by skill level or topic, accompanied by a table of contents for user convenience.

4.3 Training products design and development

The design and development phases often go in parallel. Without a good design plan, developing a course can lead to many frustrating moments and to an ineffective training programme.

³ <https://slejournal.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40561-024-00350-5>

⁴ <https://slejournal.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40561-024-00350-5>

⁵ Anderson L. W., Krathwohl D. R., A Taxonomy for Learning, Teaching, and Assessing: A Revision of Bloom's Taxonomy of Educational Objectives, Longman, 2001

After the identification of the needs, the analysis of the audience, the establishment of learning objectives, and the outline of the sequence, this is the phase that defines how to convey the message to the audience and what are the most suitable methods to help learners achieve the learning objectives. Depending on the selected approach, there are many options, methods, tools and techniques available to convey a message and facilitate learning. Selecting the appropriate method is critical to maximise engagement and ensure that knowledge and skills are not only effectively transferred, but also retained in the long term. Various approaches, such as workshops, e-learning, scenario-based simulations, hands-on sessions, and blended learning, can be considered based on the training objectives, audience, and available resources. This step should also cater to different learning styles to enhance the overall effectiveness of the training. The instructional strategy will help identify the time and space needed, as well as the materials to be developed.

The development phase focuses on the definition of the instructional strategy (including the selection of training methods) and on the actual creation (production) of the content and learning materials that will be used during the training. It is usually the longest phase in the instructional process and, even more importantly, it requires to constantly look back at the outcomes of the previous phases, in order to ensure to develop a course “with the end-users in mind”.

Training contents should be structured around the established objectives, including relevant information, skills and concepts. This step involves creating training materials such as manuals, presentations, instructional videos, activities and assessments, that support learning objectives and facilitate practical application.

Training material may take many different forms, such as workbooks, manuals, or audio and visual aids. The selection of training materials depends on the learning objectives and duration of the programme. Once the approach is defined and training methods are selected, it is time to focus on the development of training materials. The creation of the content and learning material may involve several people, such as subject matter experts, technical developers, etc. It is crucial to be ready to work in a team and open to the benefits of this collaborative process.

4.4 Training implementation and evaluation

The implementation phase is when it all comes together. Implementation is about delivering the training and ensuring that learners achieve the objectives defined during the design phase. Trainers need not only to ensure that knowledge and skills are transferred, but also that they are retained by learners, and eventually applied to their jobs, contributing to bring about a desired change at the organizational level.

Successful implementation depends on proper preparation. Preparation involves different steps that allow the delivery of a successful session. Effective training delivery requires a well-structured plan that

addresses logistical arrangements, including scheduling, trainer selection, and facility organization. Additionally, mechanisms for assessing learners during and after the training should be implemented to measure knowledge transfer and behavioural change.

The final phase of the Training Cycle is the evaluation, which assesses the effectiveness of the training program. This involves measuring whether the training achieved its learning objectives, evaluating participants' engagement, and identifying areas for improvement to inform future training initiatives.

Evaluation is an essential source of information and its importance cannot be overestimated. In general terms, evaluation refers to a systematic and objective assessment of an ongoing or completed project, programme or policy, its design, implementation and results. The aim of evaluation is to determine the relevance and fulfilment of objectives, efficiency, effectiveness, impact and sustainability.

It should focus on assessing whether the training was:

- Relevant – i.e. it met the needs and expectations of learners;
- Effective – i.e. it enabled learners to achieve learning objectives;
- Impactful – i.e. it shaped learners' knowledge, skills and attitudes in a way that would bring about the anticipated change.

Evaluation is crucial to improve training design and implementation, as it allows making informed decisions about future interventions. One of the most relevant training evaluation models is the one developed by Donald Kirkpatrick. The Kirkpatrick model systematizes the process of evaluation along four progressive levels: reaction, learning, application and results.

Level I evaluation measures the immediate reaction of learners to the training. This type of evaluation aims at assessing their immediate response to the delivery (including trainers and training methods), the materials and the logistical arrangements.

Level II evaluation measures the increase in knowledge, skills and attitudes. Simply put, it assesses how much learners have learnt from the training.

Level III evaluation, often referred to as evaluation of behavior or evaluation of application, assesses if and how the behaviour of learners has changed after the completion of the course. It focus on identifying changes in behaviour following the course and address the question: to what extent have the knowledge and skills acquired in the training or activity been applied on the job or in the life of learners?

The last level, level IV, is results evaluation (often called impact evaluation as well) and focuses on the long-term effects of the training. It assesses if and how learners' changed behaviour has influenced their organisation, community, immediate and working environment. It also attempts to determine how much of this change can be directly attributed to the training. Furthermore, impact evaluation considers unintended consequences, whether positive or negative. It is the most complex and challenging level of evaluation,

Since it often extends beyond the direct scope of trainers and may require broader institutional involvement and longer-term follow-up.

Chapter 5

Suggestions for a M4C Training Plan

5. Suggestions for a M4C Training Plan

The information gathered through the survey on the needs for training of facility/service managers, service users, and trainers in relation to the Transnational Access, along with insights from one-to-one conversations with the relevant stakeholders and WPs, has made it possible to identify a number of potential target audiences while also suggesting some training initiatives that may address the specific needs of each one of them.

The identified target audiences seem to be:

- trainers;
- facility/service managers;
- users at the installation level, or service users.

The suggested training actions for these audiences may focus on:

- M4C catalogue of services;
- M4C catalogue;
- M4C access platform and procedures;
- M4C services tutorials.

Cross-cutting topics for additional training actions may deal with:

- technical knowledge;
- laboratory safety;
- data analysis;
- reporting and sharing.

Throughout the delivery of these training activities, regardless of these being face-to-face, online or blended/hybrid, the M4C project and partners are likely to need an online training platform that can support the training delivery, as well as host the training contents developed throughout the project. A proposal in this sense could come from the partner LifeWatch ERIC, that maintains its online Training Platform and offers project-dedicated sections on it, enhancing accessibility and visibility of training contents while at the same time ensuring their sustainability in the long run, as it can guarantee training contents availability even after projects ends.

Chapter 6

Conclusions

6. Conclusions

Deliverable 7.4 provides a comprehensive and structured set of guidelines, focusing on knowledge, skills and best practices related to training principles, methodologies and expertise. These guidelines are intended to support M4C project partners in the design, development and delivery of their training activities within the project. If properly followed, and integrated in the proposed activities, these guidelines should lead to the development of high-quality training products that can contribute to improvement and innovation first within the participating RIs and second among all relevant stakeholders.

These guidelines provide a framework for the development and delivery of participatory, engaging, impactful, and relevant training activities that effectively meet the identified training needs. Similarly, the deliverable also presents an evaluation framework for training activities that is aimed at assessing whether the proposed training activities produced the expected results in terms of transfer and retainment of knowledge, skills and expertise of training participants.

Following this set of guidelines in their training design, development and delivery M4C participating RIs should be better positioned to address knowledge and skill gaps, promote effective training experiences and enhance the end users and stakeholders transnational access, thus playing an essential role in effective engagement of stakeholders and the achievement of the overall goal of the project and of the respective participating RIs.

Chapter 7

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